

THE EFFECT OF INDENTOR GEOMETRY ON THE INDENTATION RESISTANCE OF AUXETIC CARBON FIBRE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fibre laminates were produced with matched through-the-thickness modulus, but with negative (auxetic), positive and near zero Poisson's ratios. These were indented with noses of diameter 2, 12.7 and 20mm. Enhancements in indentation resistance were seen for the auxetic laminates with smaller, more localised damage areas for the two larger diameter indentors. Little difference was seen in mechanical properties for the 2mm diameter indenter.

Keywords: auxetic; indentation resistance; carbon fibre laminates; negative Poisson's ratio

INTRODUCTION

Auxetic materials are those which possess a negative Poisson's ratio, ν [1], and which, consequently, exhibit enhancements in mechanical properties such as low velocity impact resistance [2] and energy absorption [3]. A wide range of synthetic auxetic materials can be produced, but these often require complicated post processing [4] or processing at non-standard conditions. For example, auxetic fibres are produced at low temperatures (close to the polymer melting temperature) and slow speeds [5]. However, there are a class of auxetic materials which can be produced using off-the-shelf materials and conventional processing temperatures. These are auxetic fibre reinforced composites.

Generating an auxetic composite laminate requires both a particular stacking sequence and that the individual ply material be highly anisotropic. It is for this reason that the majority of research work has concentrated on carbon fibre laminates, though it should be noted that it is possible to design auxetic Kevlar laminates [6] and filament wound tubes [7] and even glass fibre laminates [8], where the Poisson's ratio is reported to be negative in-plane. For carbon fibre laminates, it is possible to design laminates with the auxetic effect either in-plane or through-the-thickness [9-11]. Previous work has shown that the fracture toughness [9,12], indentation resistance [2,13] and low velocity impact resistance [14] are all enhanced when auxetic laminates are compared with laminates of matched through-the-thickness modulus but varying Poisson's ratio. The auxetic laminates were found to sustain higher loads to failure, absorb more energy and have more localised damage.

This paper studies the effect of indenter geometry on the indentation resistance of auxetic carbon fibre laminates. Following on from the previous work, three laminate types were considered – one with a negative Poisson’s ratio, one with a near zero Poisson’s ratio and one with a positive Poisson’s ratio. Indentors of diameter 2mm, 12.7mm and 20mm were used and the effects analysed using extensive fractography. For the 2mm diameter indenter, very similar results were seen in terms of mechanical properties whereas for the larger two indenter diameters, enhancements in load sustained and energy absorbed were seen. For all three systems, the damage areas for the auxetic laminates were smaller, more localised and showed fewer delaminations.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Production of laminates

Laminates were produced from IM7/5882 unidirectional carbon epoxy prepreg using standard vacuum bagging techniques. The laminate stacking sequences which were used in this work are shown in Table 1, together with software predictions for moduli and Poisson’s ratio.

Table 1. Laminate stacking sequences and software predictions

Stacking sequence	E_1 (GPa)	E_2 (GPa)	E_3 (GPa)	ν_{13}
$([0/-45/5/40]_s)_3$	75.3	20.1	9.6	0.086
$[+/-30]_{6s}$	49.6	11.9	9.5	-0.156
$[35/-20/25/40/-85/40/25/-45/35/-15/25/40]_s$	49.8	25.0	9.6	0.187

Square panels of dimensions 80x80x3mm were prepared. A vacuum pressure of 0.8bar was applied overnight to consolidate the laminates which were then placed in a fan oven. The temperature was raised at a rate of 2-3°C/min until 180°C was reached. This was maintained for 130 minutes before the oven and contents were then slowly cooled to room temperature, the vacuum removed and the bag opened.

Indentation tests

Tests were carried out using a specially designed configuration which allowed the laminates to flex without the confines of clamping whilst also allowing the indentation nose to penetrate through the specimen. This configuration was also used by Caprino, Langella and Lopresto [15] to measure the penetration energy of carbon fibre laminates using a variety of indenter geometries.

For the tests conducted here, the indenter was applied to the centre of the surface of the simply supported specimens at a rate of 2mm/min using a Dartec Universal Hydraulic testing facility set up in compression mode. Three indentors were used, with diameters of 2mm, 12.7mm and 20mm. Tests were conducted for the 2mm diameter indenter until complete penetration, which corresponded to an indentation depth of 4mm. For the 12.7mm diameter indenter, a 5mm indentation depth was used for the same purpose.

However, for the 20mm indenter, severe bending occurred and so tests were conducted until catastrophic failure and not to any defined depth. From the load/displacement plots obtained during these tests, the load, displacement and energy absorbed at first failure and to peak load were obtained.

Fractography

In order to observe the effects of the 2mm and 12.7mm diameter indentors, a section from each sample tested was taken along the 0° fibre direction using a diamond coated rotary cutter. The samples were then cleaned, polished and observed using optical microscopy. The damage caused by the 20mm diameter indenter was too extensive to observe in this manner.

RESULTS

Tables 2 and 3 show that for the nose diameters of 12.7 and 20mm diameters, enhancements in the load sustained and energy absorbed were seen. For the 2mm diameter indenter, very similar results were seen. The Tables are composed of average values from 4 tests per configuration.

Table 2 Indentation properties to first failure for the laminates tested

Indenter size (mm)	Positive v		Near zero v		Negative v	
	Load (kN)	Energy (J)	Load (kN)	Energy (J)	Load (kN)	Energy (J)
2	2.06	0.97	1.89	0.75	1.88	0.98
12.7	3.02	1.83	2.42	1.37	3.48	2.38
20	2.59	1.27	2.85	1.50	2.87	1.61

Table 3 Indentation properties to full specimen damage for the laminates tested

Indenter size (mm)	Positive v		Near zero v		Negative v	
	Load (kN)	Energy (J)	Load (kN)	Energy (J)	Load (kN)	Energy (J)
2	3.26	5	3.09	5	3.00	5
12.7	6.77	12	6.25	10	7.70	14
20	7.47	14	8.61	16	10.27	28

These results are clearly shown in Figures 1-3, which plot 1 typical example of the load against displacement for the three laminate types tested using the 2mm (Figure 1), 12.7mm (Figure 2) and 20mm (Figure 3) diameter indentors.

Figure 1. Load/displacement plots for the 2mm diameter indenter.

Figure 2. Load/displacement plots for the 12.7mm diameter indenter

Figure 3. Load/displacement plots for the 20mm diameter indenter

Figures 4 and 5 show the fractographic damage obtained for the 2mm and 12.7mm diameter indentors for each of the laminate types. Figure 4, concentrating on the 2mm diameter indenter, shows in each case that there is significant damage, characterised by fibre breakage and matrix cracking. Delaminations have occurred towards the back face, with the near zero and positive Poisson's ratio samples showing 38mm and 35mm respectively as their extents of visible damage. For the auxetic sample, this is just 18mm, indicating that damage is more localised directly under the loading nose in this case.

Figure 4a Fractography for the 2mm diameter indenter – near zero Poisson's ratio specimen

Figure 4b Fractography for the 2mm diameter indenter – negative Poisson's ratio specimen

Figure 4c Fractography for the 2mm diameter indenter – positive Poisson's ratio specimen

Figure 5, concentrating on the 12.7mm diameter indenter, shows once again that the auxetic samples have a smaller, more localised damage area. In this case, the extent of visible damage is 37mm for the near zero Poisson's ratio laminate, 36mm for the positive Poisson's ratio laminate and just 25mm for the auxetic laminate.

Figure 5a Fractography for the 12.7mm diameter indenter – near zero Poisson's ratio specimen

Figure 5b Fractography for the 12.7mm diameter indenter – negative Poisson's ratio specimen

Figure 5c Fractography for the 12.7mm diameter indenter – positive Poisson's ratio specimen

DISCUSSION

All the laminates when indented show the typical progression of damage as illustrated by the load/displacement curves [15]. The end of the elastic phase is signified by a load drop due to intralamimar cracks generating delamination at the interlayers. After first failure, the load increases again, but with reduced stiffness indicated by a reduction in the gradient of the graph. The series of load drops on the curve are indicators of failures in both the fibres and the resin until peak load is reached. It is expected that as the diameter of the indenter increases, so does the load sustained [15] and this is indeed the case except for the first failure point of the auxetic laminate indented with the 12.7mm diameter indenter, which is higher than that for the 20mm diameter indenter. This is believed to be due to the severe bending response for these samples when using a 20mm diameter indenter.

For the 12.7mm and 20mm diameter indentors, the auxetic laminates show enhanced mechanical properties over the other two types whereas for the 2mm diameter indentor, results are very similar. This can be explained by looking at the damage mechanisms at play in each case. For a sharp indentor, it is known that failure is dominated by fibre breakage, whereas increasing the diameter of the indentor leads to failure dominated by delamination [16]. Auxetic composites have been shown previously [14] to exhibit a response which leads to suppression of delamination growth, similar to that seen in auxetic foams [17]. The effect in composites is caused by a combination of enhanced shear modulus leading to an improved material response and allowing a wider distribution of strain, and the mismatch between individual lamina layers for a [+/_30] layup leading to an orderly progression of damage and a greater communication of shear strain, giving higher resistance to delamination [18]. Thus, when the response is dominated by delamination as is the case for the larger indentor diameters, enhancements in response are to be expected and are indeed seen. For the 2mm diameter indentor, where fibre breakage is the dominant mechanism of failure, it is expected that similar results would be seen across the three laminate configurations and again, this is the case.

CONCLUSION

Enhancements in load sustained and energy absorbed were obtained for indentation tests carried out on auxetic laminates using a 12.7mm and a 20mm diameter indentor. This is because delamination, which is the dominant failure mechanism for these indentor geometries, is suppressed for the auxetic laminates, leading to higher mechanical properties and smaller damage areas. For a 2mm indentor, very similar results were seen as failure here is dominated by fibre breakage.

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